

EOSC WITHIN NATIONAL STRATEGIES FOR DIGITAL SKILLS

Consultation & Focus Group Report

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1
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Contents

1	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	7
2	REPORT ON THE CONSULTATION FOR EOSC POSITIONING IN NATIONAL POLICIES.....	8
2.1	CONSULTATION ON EOSC POSITIONING IN NATIONAL POLICIES	8
2.2	OBJECTIVES OF THE REPORT.....	9
2.3	FINDINGS AND RESULTS PER SECTION OF THE CONSULTATION	9
2.3.1	<i>Respondent's Information</i>	<i>9</i>
2.3.1.1	Country in which the participants are mainly based for work.....	9
2.3.1.2	Type of organisations that participated in the consultation.....	10
2.3.1.3	Key domain the participants are more familiar.....	11
2.3.2	<i>Section 1: Identified gaps related to the four "building blocks (BB)" of the Digital Skills (DS) & Open Science (OS) ecosystem.....</i>	<i>11</i>
2.3.2.1	Ranking of identified Gaps in Digital Skills (DS) and Open Science (OS) domains: People & Actors of EOSC	11
2.3.2.2	Ranking of identified Gaps in Digital Skills (DS) and Open Science (OS) domains: Processes & Governance.....	16
2.3.2.3	Ranking of identified Gaps in Digital Skills (DS) and Open Science (OS) domains: Policies	21
2.3.2.4	Ranking of identified Gaps in Digital Skills (DS) and Open Science (OS) domains: Technologies & infrastructure.....	25
2.3.3	<i>Section 2: Key action areas related to integrating EOSC objectives to national policies.....</i>	<i>31</i>
2.3.3.1	Key Topic 1: Digital skills required for researchers and the role of university curricula in building profiles & capacities	31
2.3.3.2	Key Topic 2: Embed EOSC principles into the career development of researchers.....	38
2.3.3.3	Key Topic 3: Collaboration of Research, Public Sector, and Industry on Open Data	41
2.3.3.4	Key Topic 4: Utilisation of existing human & technical infrastructures for developing learning environments.....	46
2.3.3.5	Key Topic 5: The role of EOSC related skills in institutional, national, thematic, industry Digital Competence Centres in the wider national scheme	50
3	REPORT ON THE FOCUS GROUP FOR EOSC POSITIONING IN NATIONAL POLICIES.....	55
3.1	SCOPE OF THE FOCUS GROUP	55
3.2	METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK.....	55
3.3	FOCUS GROUP FINDINGS	56
3.4	FOCUS GROUPS' LIST OF PARTICIPANTS	63

Table of charts

Chart 1. Countries’ Participation in the Consultation	9
Chart 2. Organisations’ Participation in the Consultation	10
Chart 3. Fields of expertise in the Consultation.....	11
Chart 4. Identified Gaps in the section People & Actors related to EOSC digital skills.....	13
Chart 5. Most important identified gaps in the section People & Actors related to EOSC digital skills	15
Chart 6. Identified Gaps in the section Processes & Governance related to EOSC digital skills.....	18
Chart 7. Most important identified gaps in the section Processes & Governance related to EOSC digital skills	19
Chart 8. Identified Gaps in the section Policies related to EOSC digital skills.....	22
Chart 9. Most important identified gaps in the section Policies related to EOSC digital skills.....	24
Chart 10. Identified Gaps in the section Technologies & Infrastructure related to EOSC digital skills	28
Chart 11. Most important identified gaps in the section Technologies & Infrastructure related to EOSC digital skills	29
Chart 12. Kinds of (digital) skills are needed for researchers	32
Chart 13. Most important types of (digital) skills for researchers.....	34
Chart 14. Role of university curricula in building profiles/ capacities	37
Chart 15. Most important actions of Universities in(digital) skills for researchers	38
Chart 16. Actions for embedding EOSC principles in researchers’ career development	40
Chart 17. Most important actions for embedding EOSC principles in researchers’ career development	41
Chart 18. Actions for Research, Public Sector and Industry best collaboration on open data.....	45
Chart 19. Most important actions for the collaboration of Research/Public Sector/Industry.....	46
Chart 20. Actions for human and technical infrastructure to support the development of learning environments.....	49
Chart 21. Most important actions for the use of human & technical infrastructure for the development of learning environments	50
Chart 22. Actions for EOSC to enhance (digital) skills for researchers through the Digital Competences Centres.....	53
Chart 23. Most important actions for EOSC enhancing (digital) skills for researchers through the Digital Competences Centres.....	54

Abbreviations

AC	Associated Countries
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESCO	European Skills, Competences, Qualifications & Occupation
EU	European Union
ICT	Information & Communications Technology
IT	Information Technology
LLL	Lifelong Learning
MS	Member States
SRIA	Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda
TGB	Technopolis Group Belgium

6
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1 Executive Summary

Following the implementation of the landscape and gap analysis, and based on the results of these previous tasks as well as the emerging EOSC SRIA and Partnership documents, a structured consultation took place in November 2020 to provide insights on how to best position EOSC Skills and Training in Digital Skills in national strategies and agendas and to form the basis for developing a list of relevant recommendations for various types of policy makers. The consultation was based on two sections whereas the 1st one corresponded to identified gaps related to four "building blocks (BB)" of the Digital Skills (DS) & Open Science (OS) ecosystem (namely **People & Actors of EOSC, Processes & Governance, Policies and Technologies & infrastructure**) and the 2nd one explored the key action areas related to integrating EOSC objectives to national policies.

65 participants from 22 countries participated in the consultation, the majority of which come from the higher education and research community that are more involved and concerned with integrating EOSC skills and principles into national strategies and policies for digital upskilling.

Participants were asked to rank in terms of perceived relevance to the EOSC objectives all the gaps identified during the gap analysis phase and to nominate according to their opinion on the most pressing one for each of the above Building Blocks. They also proposed gaps that were not originally present in the consultation as relevant to the EOSC digital skills initiatives.

Furthermore, participants were asked to rank for relevance a list of provided answers for the following topics/ questions that address key aspects regarding EOSC objectives and are considered important towards elaboration of recommendations to establish EOSC positioning: 1. Digital skills required for researchers and the role of university curricula in building profiles & capacities, 2. Embed EOSC principles into the career development of researchers, Collaboration of Research, Public Sector, and Industry on Open Data, 4. Utilisation of existing human & technical infrastructures for developing learning environments and 5. The role of EOSC related skills in institutional, national, thematic, industry Digital Competence Centres in the wider national scheme.

Studying and analysis of the results (presented in this report in an easily readable graphic format) lead to the identification of 11 key areas as the basis for subsequent recommendations on EOSC positioning in national strategies. To this end, a focus group was organised in December 2020 with 17 experts from 12 countries to discuss and comment on the afore mentioned topics. They experts covered and provided expertise on policies, FAIR & Openness, EOSC leadership, researchers upskilling, researchers' career development, digital skills qualification, research ethical practice, learning environments/technologies and infrastructure, citizen's science, research upskilling governance, cross-disciplinary cooperation (research/public/industry).

The findings, presented in this report in the form of comments to proposed answers on the 11 key topics, were further analysed and lead to the final set of recommendations to be elaborated by our team to form the final deliverable of the study.

2 Report on the Consultation for EOSC Positioning in National Policies

2.1 Consultation on EOSC Positioning in National Policies

Following the implementation of the landscape and gap analysis, and based on the results of these previous tasks as well as the emerging EOSC SRIA and Partnership documents, a structured consultation, took place to provide insights on the following aspects:

- Data intensive science and open science: role and connection with public and industry sectors
- Data profiles in research track. Role of university curricula in building profiles/ capacities
- Role and placement of EOSC related skills in institutional, national, thematic, industry Digital Competence Centres in the wider national scheme. Special consideration for HPC and AI related competence centers was given
- Best use of existing human and technical infrastructure (e.g., libraries, data centres)

Overall, the objective of the consultation was to analyse and provide insights on how to best position EOSC Skills and Training in Digital Skills in national strategies and agendas (advocacy), as well as to develop a list for recommendations for various types of policy makers, with the purpose of providing well-rounded, all-inclusive (research-government-industry-public) options to include in national strategies for Digital Skills and up-skilling.

The consultation was divided into two sections as follows:

Section 1 corresponded to identified gaps related to four "building blocks (BB)" of the Digital Skills (DS) & Open Science (OS) ecosystem:

- **BB1- People & Actors of EOSC:** The scope is to assess and prioritise the relevance and significance of gaps identified in relation with existing academic curricula and accreditation systems for data scientists and public employees, with existing standardisation practices for digital skills profiles, with existing educational modules on open science and open data practices in the universities' curricula or other ongoing training systems, as well as with the any rewarding process for career development of researchers on open science practices and cross-sector (research-industry-public sector) cooperation mechanisms.
- **BB2- Processes & Governance:** The scope is to assess and prioritise the relevance and significance of gaps identified in relation with existing coordination and regulatory mechanisms for digital skills development and for open data, open science, AI, cybersecurity skills development, as well as with existing private sector - research cooperation structures.
- **BB3- Policies:** The scope is to assess and prioritise the relevance and significance of gaps identified in relation with existing policies and strategies dedicated to digital skills and training, open data, open science, AI, and cybersecurity.
- **BB4- Technologies & infrastructure:** The scope is to assess and prioritise the relevance and significance of gaps identified in relation with existing national training platforms and content development structures as well as with existing advanced learning environments applying open data principles and mechanisms for researchers' cooperation based on open science principles.

Section 2 explored the key action areas related to integrating EOSC objectives to national policies.

For this purpose, and for supporting the consultation participants in their feedback, a questionnaire was developed (<https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/news-opinion/consultation-eosc-digital-skills>), designed in a way to take not more than 20 minutes.

The consultation targeted all interested stakeholders from the public and private sectors, including Governmental Organisations, Universities, Libraries, Research Institutes/ Agencies. Research Funding

Organisations, Initiative/ Programme’s representatives, EOSC, the European Commission, National Coalitions, Committees/ Councils and Private sector/ Industry organisations.

The consultation was conducted from Thursday 19 November 2020 until Friday 27 November 2020 and overall, 65 responses were collected.

2.2 Objectives of the Report

The objective of the Consultation Analysis report is to process, analyse and present the results of the consultation. The report takes stock of the contributions and presents preliminary trends that emerge from them, focusing on quantitative aspects.

2.3 Findings and results per section of the Consultation

2.3.1 Respondent's Information

2.3.1.1 Country in which the participants are mainly based for work

Chart 1. Countries’ Participation in the Consultation

Among the 65 responses 8 participants (12,3%) are based in the United Kingdom, 7 in France (10,8%), 5 in Greece (7,7%), 5 in Netherlands (7,7%), 16 participants are based in Austria, Czech Republic, Ireland and Serbia (4 participants or 6,2% in each country), 9 participants are based in Germany, Spain and Italy (3 participants or 4,6% in each country), 8 participants are based in Denmark, Poland, Bosnia Herzegovina and Montenegro (2 participants or 3,1% in each country), and 7 participants are based in Bulgaria, Hungary, Slovakia, Armenia, Norway, Switzerland and Turkey (1 participant or 1,5% in each country).

It is pointed out that with regards to the preselected countries, that participated in the landscape analysis, all of them also participated in the consultation process, apart from Lithuania and Portugal.

Overall, there is **wide dispersion observed at country level, where 22 countries participated in the consultation process**, out of which 16 are Member States and 8 are Associated countries, which indicates the importance of integrating EOSC Skills and Training in Digital Skills in national strategies and agendas around the EU.

2.3.1.2 Type of organisations that participated in the consultation

Regarding the type of organizations that participated in the consultation process, 35 (or 54%) responses came from universities, 18 (or 27%) responses came from research institutes and agencies, 3 (5%) responses from the private sector/industry, 2 (or 3%) responses came from initiative/programmes’ representatives, 2 (or 3%) responses came from regional training and research units, while there was one response (or 1,5%) coming from a research funding organization, one from a governmental organization, one from a National Coalition on Digital Skills and Jobs, one from a higher education institute other than university and one from a research library.

Chart 2. Organisations’ Participation in the Consultation

These results indicate that **almost all responses (89%) came from the higher education and research community** (universities, research institutes and other related entities), which represent the entities that are more involved and concerned with integrating EOSC skills and principles into national strategies and policies for digital upskilling. This drives the consultation results to a more targeted opinion related to the research area rather than the digital skills area.

2.3.1.3 Key domain the participants are more familiar

Out of the 65 participants in the consultation process, 27 (or 42%) stated that are more familiar with the Open Science domain, 12 (or 18%) stated that are more familiar with the Digital Skills domain, while 26 (or 40%) stated that are familiar with both domains.

Chart 3. Fields of expertise in the Consultation

Though the percentage of the participants with primary familiarity with digital skills is rather low (18%), it is high enough to reflect the views and considerations of that particular domain, outside the research and higher education field.

2.3.2 Section 1: Identified gaps related to the four "building blocks (BB)" of the Digital Skills (DS) & Open Science (OS) ecosystem

2.3.2.1 Ranking of identified Gaps in Digital Skills (DS) and Open Science (OS) domains: People & Actors of EOSC

This first section related to the building block: People & Actors of EOSC, presents the ranking of the identified gaps in the general Digital Skills domain (DS) and the specific Open Science domain (OS), as derived between findings from the Landscape study and EOSC objectives.

Participants were asked to rate each identified gap from a grade of 1 (least important) to 5 (most important), while afterwards they were asked to choose one of the highest ranked gaps to identify as the most important to tackle.

According to the participants responses all of the identified gaps were validated and ranked as important or highly important, while there were very limited cases where some of the gaps were characterised as unimportant or irrelevant.

There were also some case where the identified gaps were characterised neither important nor unimportant (neutral) which include:

- DS.1.4: Absence of National Competences Framework related to digital skills
- OS.1.1: Most courses offered by universities are not "fit for purpose" courses towards Open Science and FAIRness principles
- OS.1.4: Absence of guidelines to help policy makers develop and formalize clear career pathways to target researcher profiles close to Open Science principles.
- OS.1.5: Undergoing development of collaborating mechanisms (academia, industry, government) with weak coordination for the development of profiles

The results are presented in the following two graphs.

12
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Chart 4. Identified Gaps in the section People & Actors related to EOSC digital skills

13
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Chart 5. Most important identified gaps in the section People & Actors related to EOSC digital skills

15

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According to the participants responses **the most pressing identified Gaps** are

- OS.1.2: Absence of established clear, specific incentives for complying with Open Science principles
- DS.1.1: Very few curricula related to advanced, core expertise data skills for researchers

while there were several responses that placed importance on the gaps:

- OS.1.4: Absence of guidelines to help policy makers develop and formalize clear career pathways to target researcher profiles close to Open Science principles.
- DS.1.2: Little advanced training was identified to be targeting researchers

Moreover, **there were two additional gaps identified by the participants**, which entail a) the lack of interest on the part of policy makers, even if relevant guidelines for policy makers and good practice examples are available, policy makers either are not aware of their existence and/or are not interested in implementing them and b) the absence of cohesive integration of "Big Data" with Open Science, with Computer Science and Computational Science with AI and HPC.

2.3.2.2 *Ranking of identified Gaps in Digital Skills (DS) and Open Science (OS) domains: Processes & Governance*

This second section related to the building block: Processes & Governance, presents the ranking of the identified gaps in the general Digital Skills domain (DS) and the specific Open Science domain (OS), as derived between findings from the Landscape study and EOSC objectives.

Participants were asked to rate each identified gap from a grade of 1 (least important) to 5 (most important), while afterwards they were asked to choose one of the highest ranked gaps to identify as the most important to tackle.

According to the participants responses all of the identified gaps were validated and ranked as important or highly important, while there were very limited cases where some of the gaps were characterised as unimportant or irrelevant.

There were also some case where the identified gaps were characterised neither important nor unimportant (neutral) which include:

- DS.2.3: Fragmentation of the governance system for the upgrade of digital skills
- DS.2.4: Absence of an integrated legislative/regulatory framework addressing the digital skills and competences building
- DS.2.5: Limited role of the National Coalitions for Digital Skills in coordinating of all digital upskilling initiatives

The results are presented in the following two graphs.

Identified Gaps in BB2: Processes & Governance

17
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Chart 6. Identified Gaps in the section Processes & Governance related to EOSC digital skills

18

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2. GOVERNANCE/ PROCESSES

Chart 7. Most important identified gaps in the section Processes & Governance related to EOSC digital skills

19
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According to the participants responses **the most pressing identified Gaps** are

- OS.2.2: Need for establishing legislation on open science/access or open data, with a statutory scheme on data
- OS.2.3: Weak cooperation among research–public–private domains, fostering the application of research and innovation and governance structures of blended type

while there were several responses that placed importance on the gaps:

- DS.2.1: Absence of a unified approach and coordination on digital skills development
- OS.2.1: Data Ethics very rarely tackled
- DS.2.2: Different approaches and techniques for digital skills and competences' interdisciplinarity
- DS.2.3: Fragmentation of the governance system for the upgrade of digital skills

Moreover, **there was one additional gap identified by the participants**, which entails the EU's DGs lack of transversal view of citizens Life -Long learning (LLL) to improve policies and competences/skills from a LLL perspective.

2.3.2.3 Ranking of identified Gaps in Digital Skills (DS) and Open Science (OS) domains: Policies

The third section related to the building block: Policies, presents the ranking of the identified gaps in the general Digital Skills domain (DS) and the specific Open Science domain (OS), as derived between findings from the Landscape study and EOSC objectives.

Participants were asked to rate each identified gap from a grade of 1 (least important) to 5 (most important), while afterwards they were asked to choose one of the highest ranked gaps to identify as the most important to tackle.

According to the participants responses all of the identified gaps were validated and ranked as important or highly important, while there were very limited cases where some of the gaps were characterised as unimportant or irrelevant.

There were also some case where the identified gaps were characterised neither important nor unimportant (neutral) which include:

- OS.3.1: No coordination in the consolidation of initiatives to policy level
- DS.3.3: The level of dispersion of digital skills initiatives in other national policies related to EOSC (e.g., AI and cybersecurity) is rather low
- DS.3.1: Absence of a unified approach for stand-alone national digital skills strategies

The results are presented in the following two graphs.

Chart 8. Identified Gaps in the section Policies related to EOSC digital skills

3. POLICIES

Chart 9. Most important identified gaps in the section Policies related to EOSC digital skills

24
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According to the participants responses **the most pressing identified Gaps** are:

- OS.3.2: Need for developing and adapting an open science policy at national level
- DS.3.2: Priorities of different actors of the digital skills ecosystem do not consider open science upskilling needs.

while there were several responses that placed importance on the gaps:

- OS.3.3: Limited elaboration of open data/science principles' enhancement in Artificial Intelligence and Cybersecurity domains
- OS.3.1: No coordination in the consolidation of initiatives to policy level
- DS.3.3: The level of dispersion of digital skills initiatives in other national policies related to EOSC (e.g. AI and cybersecurity) is rather low

Moreover, **there was one additional gap identified by the participants**, which entails the insufficient development of information technologies policies applied to data and science context

2.3.2.4 *Ranking of identified Gaps in Digital Skills (DS) and Open Science (OS) domains: Technologies & infrastructure*

This forth section related to the building block: Technologies & infrastructure, presents the ranking of the identified gaps in the general Digital Skills domain (DS) and the specific Open Science domain (OS), as derived between findings from the Landscape study and EOSC objectives.

Participants were asked to rate each identified gap from a grade of 1 (least important) to 5 (most important), while afterwards they were asked to choose one of the highest ranked gaps to identify as the most important to tackle.

According to the participants responses all of the identified gaps were validated and ranked as important or highly important, while there were very limited cases where some of the gaps were characterised as unimportant or irrelevant.

There were also some case where the identified gaps were characterised neither important nor unimportant (neutral) which include:

- DS.4.2: There is no “blueprint” to follow on establishing a learning environment at national level
- DS.4.3: Different platform owners' statuses leading to different approaches for planning and developing of the content
- OS.4.1: Learning environments for Open Science digital up-skilling vary widely among the various countries in terms of scope, operations, content, infrastructures, and organisation

The results are presented in the following two graphs.

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Identified Gaps in BB4: Technologies & Infrastructure

Chart 10. Identified Gaps in the section Technologies & Infrastructure related to EOSC digital skills

4. TECHNOLOGIES/ INFRASTRUCTURE

Chart 11. Most important identified gaps in the section Technologies & Infrastructure related to EOSC digital skills

29
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According to the participants responses **the most pressing identified Gaps** are:

- OS.4.2: Few coordinated efforts to undertake the role of a central hub to foster education and training initiatives for researchers & Open Science (Competence Centre)
- OS.4.5: Absence of stakeholders' coordination for the delivery and use of content platforms/learning environments

while there were several responses that placed importance on the gaps:

- DS.4.2: There is no “blueprint” to follow on establishing a learning environment at national level
- OS.4.1: Learning environments for Open Science digital up-skilling vary widely among the various countries in terms of scope, operations, content, infrastructures and organisation
- OS.4.3: Absence of consolidated available resources to be considered as formal, monitored and managed learning environments

Moreover, **there were two additional gaps identified by the participants**, which entail a) the lack of global EU thematic repositories, to avoid n-plication and lack of some for some scientific specialties and b) the indexing and disseminating consolidated and monitored content.

2.3.3 Section 2: Key action areas related to integrating EOSC objectives to national policies

Under this section of the consultation process, the participants were asked to rank possible answers provided on a scale of 1 (least relevant) to 3 (most relevant) for the following topics/ questions that address key aspects regarding EOSC objectives and are considered important towards elaboration of recommendations to establish EOSC positioning. For each question, the participants were also given the option to add more suggestions per topic.

2.3.3.1 Key Topic 1: Digital skills required for researchers and the role of university curricula in building profiles & capacities

Key Topic 1 explored the options on the digital skills required for researchers and the role of university curricula in building profiles & capacities.

The first key topic included two main questions for the participants to address:

- What kind of (digital) skills are needed for researchers?
- What is the role of university curricula in building profiles/ capacities?

According to the participants responses all of the possible answers that were provided to them, were validated, and ranked as relevant or highly relevant, while there were very limited cases where some of the options / answers were characterised as least relevant.

The results are presented in the following two graphs.

What kind of (digital) skills are needed for researchers?

Chart 12. Kinds of (digital) skills are needed for researchers

32
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Key Topic 1: What kind of (digital) skills are needed for researchers?

- General knowledge on the EOSC (including FAIR principles)
- Training & communication skills to teach & educate other researchers & students on how to conduct research in the framework of EOSC
- Ability to use EOSC core and EOSC exchange interdisciplinary services for data access, sharing, reuse and processing
- Ability to use EOSC discipline-specific services
- Regulatory aspects of data related to IPR and copyright

Chart 13. Most important types of (digital) skills for researchers

According to the participants responses **the options/answers that were characterised as highly relevant** are:

- General knowledge on the EOSC (including FAIR principles)
- Training and communication skills to teach and educate other researchers and students on how to conduct research in the framework of EOSC

while there were several responses that placed importance on the following options/answers:

- Ability to use EOSC core and EOSC exchange interdisciplinary services for data access, sharing, reuse and processing
- Ability to use EOSC discipline-specific services

Moreover, **there were four additional answers/suggestions identified by the participants**, which entail a) training in data ethics, data management basics and ability to select and apply trusted infrastructures and services, research workflows, collaborative work, sharing and reproducibility, b) "EOSC driving license" which means basic skills which allow use everything what researchers need and which is already offered, c) Digcomp and Entrecomp and d) understanding and applying trusted data sharing approaches.

What is the role of university curricula in building profiles/ capacities?

Chart 14. Role of university curricula in building profiles/ capacities

Key Topic 1: What is the role of university curricula in building profiles/ capacities?

Chart 15. Most important actions of Universities in(digital) skills for researchers

According to the participants responses **the options/answers that were characterised as highly relevant** are:

- Develop curricula at graduate level
- Develop Lifelong Learning courses

while there were several responses that placed importance on the following options/answers:

- Participate in networks for the development and establishment of OS profiles
- Develop curricula at undergraduate level

Moreover, **there were two additional answers/suggestions identified by the participants**, which entail a) establishing career tracks and resourcing (direct and via funding) which address the above and b) globally a greater alignment of universities with job demand is requested, an EU observatory (identify and predict demand) and national points are needed to align global demand with learning offers (national employment service and more flexible universities).

2.3.3.2 Key Topic 2: Embed EOSC principles into the career development of researchers

Key Topic 2 explored the options on how to embed EOSC principles into the career development of researchers.

In this second key topic there was one question included for the participants to address:

- How can EOSC principles be embedded in researchers' career development?

According to the participants responses all of the possible answers that were provided to them, were validated, and ranked as relevant or highly relevant, while there were very limited cases where some of the options / answers were characterised as least relevant.

The results are presented in the following two graphs.

How can EOSC principles be embedded in researchers' career development?

Chart 16. Actions for embedding EOSC principles in researchers' career development

40

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Key Topic 2: How can EOSC principles be embedded in researchers' career development?

- Reward early career researchers in evaluation process & promote recognition and reward of OS skills in recruitment and career progression
- Involve digital competence centres in specific OS training & upskilling
- Award FAIR practices with ECTS
- Engage students in participatory activities supported by learning environments
- Organise and operate a mobility network of OS research champions

Chart 17. Most important actions for embedding EOSC principles in researchers' career development

According to the participants responses **the options/answers that were characterised as highly relevant** are:

- Reward early career researchers in evaluation process & promote recognition and reward of OS skills in recruitment and career progression
- Involve digital competence centres in specific OS training & upskilling

while there were several responses that placed importance on the following options/answers:

- Award FAIR practices with ECTS
- Engage students in participatory activities supported by learning environments

Moreover, **there were five additional answers/suggestions identified by the participants**, which entail a) the existing scientific ranking methods should be updated, and a new EU ranking (with core EU values) could be created, b) involve libraries in specific OS training and skilling's (coordination between stakeholders), c) create OS annual rewards, d) award cooperation practices and e) work with the regular (National) Research Schools within each discipline (those are the places where teaching and courses are being organized for young and also established researchers and they are key for any young researcher).

2.3.3.3 Key Topic 3: Collaboration of Research, Public Sector, and Industry on Open Data

Key Topic 3 explored the options on collaboration of Research, Public Sector, and Industry on Open Data.

In this third key topic there was one question included for the participants to address:

- How Research, Public Sector and Industry can best collaborate on open data?

According to the participants responses all of the possible answers that were provided to them, were validated, and ranked as relevant or highly relevant, while there were very limited cases where some of the options / answers were characterised as least relevant.

The results are presented in the following two graphs.

42
This Study has been funded by the EOSCsecretariat.eu which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Programme call H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-4, Grant Agreement number 831644

How Research, Public Sector and Industry can best collaborate on open data?

43

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Chart 18. Actions for Research, Public Sector and Industry best collaboration on open data

45

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Key Topic 3: How Research, Public Sector and Industry can best collaborate on open data?

- Require compliance to the formal Open Science policy as prerequisite for research funding
- Make OS skills reinforcement, recognition and reward eligible for funding in research programs
- Ensure the applicability of the formal national Open Science policy
- Adopt collaborative approach in the operation of digital competence centres to promote OS skills
- Apply Open Data standards to every organization respecting GDPR & IPR limitations
- Ensure a transparent and efficient coordination of the OS ecosystem
- Establish an Open Science Network as a coordination and recommendation mechanism
- Encourage public sector Innovation Procurement related to Open Science outcomes
- Enhance OS industrial research & researcher mobility in the labour market

Chart 19. Most important actions for the collaboration of Research/Public Sector/Industry

According to the participants responses **the options/answers that were characterised as highly relevant** are:

- Require compliance to the formal Open Science policy as prerequisite for research funding
- Make OS skills reinforcement, recognition, and reward eligible for funding in research programs

while there were several responses that placed importance on the following options/answers:

- Ensure the applicability of the formal national Open Science policy
- Adopt collaborative approach in the operation of digital competence centres to promote OS skills
- Apply Open Data standards to every organization respecting GDPR & IPR limitations
- Ensure a transparent and efficient coordination of the OS ecosystem

2.3.3.4 Key Topic 4: Utilisation of existing human & technical infrastructures for developing learning environments

Key Topic 4 explored the options on the utilisation of existing human & technical infrastructures for developing learning environments.

In this fourth key topic there was one question included for the participants to address:

- How the existing human and technical infrastructure can be best used for the development of learning environments?

According to the participants responses all of the possible answers that were provided to them, were validated, and ranked as relevant or highly relevant, while there were very limited cases where some of the options / answers were characterised as least relevant.

The results are presented in the following two graphs.

How the existing human and technical infrastructure can be best used for the development of learning environments?

Chart 20. Actions for human and technical infrastructure to support the development of learning environments

Key Topic 4: How the existing human and technical infrastructure can be best used for the development of learning environments?

Chart 21. Most important actions for the use of human & technical infrastructure for the development of learning environments

According to the participants responses **the options/answers that were characterised as highly relevant** are:

- Build-up strong co-operation with research libraries on open access
- Conclude national open access license agreements with publishers
- Link national research data infrastructures to the EOSC federated system

while there were several responses that placed importance on the following options/answers:

- Set-up national research data infrastructure
- Incubate shared OS services, tools and standards

Moreover, **there were two additional answers/suggestions identified by the participants**, which entail a) communicate upon public data infrastructures policies and standards so that researchers and research teams adopt them early in research process and hopefully deposit data in these data infrastructures and b) build-up strong co-operation with others existing networks as URFIST network.

2.3.3.5 Key Topic 5: The role of EOSC related skills in institutional, national, thematic, industry Digital Competence Centres in the wider national scheme

Key Topic 5 explored the options on the role of EOSC related skills in institutional, national, thematic, industry Digital Competence Centres in the wider national scheme.

In this fifth key topic there was one question included for the participants to address:

- What is the role of EOSC related skills in institutional, national, thematic, industry Digital Competence Centres in the wider national scheme?

According to the participants responses all of the possible answers that were provided to them, were validated, and ranked as relevant or highly relevant, while there were very limited cases where some of the options / answers were characterised as least relevant.

The results are presented in the following two graphs.

51
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What is the role of EOSC related skills in institutional, national, thematic, industry Digital Competence Centres in the wider national scheme?

Chart 22. Actions for EOSC to enhance (digital) skills for researchers through the Digital Competences Centres

Key Topic 5: What is the role of EOSC related skills in institutional, national, thematic, industry in the wider national scheme?

- Co-develop different types of training courses
- Tailor generic training materials to discipline specificities
- Promote innovative ways of learning
- Propose a solid governance scheme for digital skills development to national stakeholders' market demands
- Develop a quality assurance and certification framework
- Align curricula and training with market demands
- Develop an EOSC leadership programme to foster the right policy environment for skills and training
- Devise a common framework for learning pathways

Chart 23. Most important actions for EOSC enhancing (digital) skills for researchers through the Digital Competences Centres

According to the participants responses **the options/answers that were characterised as highly relevant** are:

- Co-develop different types of training courses
- Tailor generic training materials to discipline specificities

while there were several responses that placed importance on the following options/answers:

- Promote innovative ways of learning
- Propose a solid governance scheme for digital skills development to national stakeholders' market demands

3 Report on the Focus Group for EOSC Positioning in National Policies

3.1 Scope of the Focus Group

The scope of the Focus Group relates to the fourth objective and relies on:

- providing an analysis and detailed examination of the Recommendations and the suggested Actions, for the provision of insights resulting from the opinions of the participants
- revealing a roadmap for the implementation of the above-mentioned recommendations
- elaborating conclusions for all parties involved, to feed the recommendations for EOSC positioning in National Strategies.

3.2 Methodological framework

Synthesis

The focus group was formed by 17 participants. They covered and provided expertise on the following topics: policies, FAIR & Openness, EOSC leadership, researchers upskilling, researchers' career development, digital skills qualification, research ethical practice, learning environments/technologies and infrastructure, citizen's science, research upskilling governance, cross-disciplinary cooperation (research/public/industry).

Duration

150 minutes: 15 minutes introduction, 10 minutes discussion per topic.

Process

The participants were provided with the recommendations and the suggested actions. A related short presentation initiated the focus group.

Content

There are 11 topics for discussion (recommendations), some of the topics were inter-related. The participants commented on each topic and on the suggested actions presented to them and enriched, specified, or identified any potential missing action or correction needed.

The topics are listed below:

The Key Questions asked below, are 1-1 connected to specific recommendations and play the role of guiding steps rather than questions for detailed answers provided separately by the participants:

- How can digital upskilling measures be integrated into national open science policies, fully respecting the legal, ethical and IPR aspects?
- How education and training in Open Science Principles (i.e. FAIR & Open Data/Access) can be promoted into EU policies?

- How can the use of high-quality, modular, tailor-made educational and training material for Open/Data Science (curricula, courses, on-line lessons) be developed, consolidated, disseminated and mandated, at national level?
- How can digital upskilling be complemented with a rigid readily available support network for Open Science practices and technical infrastructures, at national level?
- How can the delivery and use of content platforms and learning environments be coordinated, at national level?
- How can researchers' national career development rewarding open science practicing be supported?
- How can a national accreditation and qualification system in regard to Open Science / Data skills for all be promoted?
- How can soft skills (e.g. on ethics) be nationally enhanced to relate with Open Science principles?
- How can an integrated at national level, robust, transparent, and participatory governance structure for digital skills on open science/access be established, at national and EU level?
- How can academia, research and industry be brought together for: (a) knowledge exchange to meet companies' research and (b) innovation needs and students' and researchers cross-disciplinary gain of experience, at national level?
- How can a national framework for co-development aiming at fostering "upward convergence" in competences needed related to Open Data/Open Science be developed?
- How can the development of Citizen Science be promoted and realised, at national level?
- How can EOSC ensure its sustainability and active contribution to EU policies, through the development of an EOSC Leadership Program?

3.3 Focus Group Findings

Question 1: How can digital upskilling measures be integrated into national open science policies, fully respecting the legal, ethical and IPR aspects?

1. By developing the principles and guidelines related to a digital upskilling component on Open Science addressed to national policies, including legal, ethical and IPR related issues?
2. By adopting Measures, at national level, to ensure that various digital ecosystem actors (as organisations performing research, public and private, industry) fully comply to any established open science/data upskilling policy, especially when research funding is requested, respecting IPR issues?

Responses:

- Recommendations at EU level for MS/AC are needed however this is not enough; National Policies on Open Science should be established and components on digital and open science skills should be correlated to all other related national policies (i.e., education). A mechanism for monitoring and evaluation these policies and interventions should be put in place
- A definition of all digital skills reference is also needed (Open Science, EOSC, digital skills, etc.)
- Research Funders should play an important role in boosting Institutions adopting related initiatives
- Open Science skills are broader than EOSC digital Skills; science communication, public engagement, working with stakeholders is also important
- Incentives are especially important both at the level of Institutions and funders; Accreditation is also particularly important as an incentive
- Policies should have tangible outcomes; pilot initiatives could precede for this.

Question 2: How education and training in Open Science Principles (e., FAIR & Open Data/Access) can be promoted into EU policies?

1. By developing Open Science Principles to be applied and included in the European Digital Education Content Framework scheduled within the Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027?
2. By developing a Digital Education Content Framework specific to Open and FAIR data, reflecting the need for interoperability, certification, verification, and transferability of content?
3. By establishing an EU legislation framework on open science, with a statutory scheme on research data and related skills
4. By promoting Open Science digital upskilling at EU and national level, via the establishment of incentives in relation to national and EU policies and interventions funding (i.e., making Open Science digital upskilling expenses eligible for funding or prerequisite for projects on researchers' overall professional advancement)

Responses:

- The EU framework is a powerful recommendation; is there readiness for this? Alternatively, guidelines with good practices of MS/AC, Institutions, Interventions could serve the purpose
- The EU framework should include copy rights for open access on research publications. The Public Sector Framework needs also to be considered
- There are a lot of initiatives for this to be considered and be integrated; Incentives might be the most effective way to proceed
- There is a lot asked for the researchers and we need to perhaps to downplay Open Science; Researchers have a lot to achieve and this should be taken into consideration for upskilling
- Not everything is open and not every should be open in science; provisions for science not being open should be included in the framework
- Open Access might not be related to skills
- Topic 4 is more related to funders; the EU dimension need to be clearer. Also, different types of incentives should be identified for individual and Institutions. Incentives for Institutions could be the driver.

Question 3: How can the use of high-quality, modular, tailor-made educational and training material for Open/Data Science (curricula, courses, on-line lessons) be developed, consolidated, disseminated and mandated, at national level?

1. By developing curricula for various programs addressed to LLL, secondary and tertiary education, regarding digital skills for Open Science?
2. By aligning educational and training material for Open/Data Science (curricula, courses, on-line lessons) to research and market demand via a system of skills 'intelligence'?
3. By developing tailored advanced courses on Open Science principles (universities)?
4. By developing a set of Implementation Guidelines for researchers and data stewards on how to actually apply Open Science principles into their everyday practice and promote "learning by doing" concepts in all relevant institutions?
5. By launching a pilot initiative to investigate innovative training techniques and tools for research training infrastructure to support upskilling?
6. By developing a mechanism encompassing 'individual learning accounts'?
7. By developing ethical guidelines on artificial intelligence (AI) and data usage in teaching and learning?

Responses:

- There is already a lot of training material deriving from initiatives undertaken by the Universities and many courses already in place. Therefore, it is best to try to integrate this educational material rather than starting brand new; Sharing training material and being FAIR in its use is important. Also rewarding for the use of the existing material on open science could be set as an incentive by the funders to avoid n-plication and 'new' development
- Enabling interoperability and harvesting across training catalogues is essential and is already being discussed in the EOSC Skills & Training WG; the importance of re-use should be recognised, but content creators need to know how best to do this. Often re-use is limited because the formats do not allow this easily (it's not just about licensing)
- Specific curricula are needed for data stewards along with professionalisation; National initiatives in data carpentries' skills and professionalisation could be explored
- Open research requires greater responsibility by the researchers themselves, so ethics and codes of conduct are important and must be part of training
- Tailoring advanced courses on Open Science principles (universities) is not needed were the differences among disciples are small; Tailored courses are needed for data carpentries
- Specific curricula might not be necessary; existing ones should be adapted to open science principles
- Harmonisation of the digital education action plans, being part of a more integrated policy on skills and open science is needed
- Trainings have many approaches; Certification and standardisation of training is important to have tangible outcomes
- Action is needed throughout the overall process: 'develop' curricula, prepare the training material, perform training
- Training infrastructure should facilitate exchange of training material: An initiative on training material being 'inter-operable' would be interesting; the same for a related Initiative for Universities' interoperability on training exchange and involving networks of Universities and trainers
- Open Science principles should be embedded to much more curricula, not only AI
- A lot is being done and in place in projects of H2020 for ethics, along with AI at EU level. This should be reflected to the topic for AI
- Also, a lot has been developed in many H2020 projects on guidelines and frameworks, and it should be used to avoid n-plication

Question 4: How can researchers' national career development rewarding open science practicing be supported?

1. By establishing the framework (research skills' taxonomy, guiding principles, governance) for the development of Open Science profiles for EOSC research actors (such as researchers and data stewards), with the aim to be incorporated in the national mechanisms/systems?
2. By providing guidelines to help national policy makers developing and formalising clear career pathways for EOSC research actors, encompassing: rewarding mechanisms close to Open Science principles, eventually speculating on the inclusion of awarding FAIR practices with ECTS, evidence-based monitoring mechanisms (including KPIs) for researchers' mobility?
3. By establishing incentives and support measures towards developing a career reward structure (capitalizing on the open science principles adoption) for all researchers, and particularly for Early Career Researchers?
4. By establishing related Regulatory Provisions?

Responses:

- Many WG have studied researchers career development and rewarding and their outcomes should be integrated, a lot has been elaborated and ready to be used; A broadly acceptable existing approach should be endorsed, plus an implementing roadmap taking no more than 2 years

- Different skill taxonomies exist and should be assessed to decide on those being most appropriate to recommend
- The DORA Declaration on research assessment should be considered within this career development framework
- Rewarding systems should be managed with HR departments in the area of education; they also need to be aligned to national accreditation and research assessment and evaluation systems, considering initiatives and guidelines at EU level. Alignment needs to be undertaken at all levels, EU, national, research funders, research institutions, stakeholders within the assessment and the evaluation of research, etc
- Credits are more appropriate than ECTS; Credits should be used to incentivise mostly students and early career researchers.

Question 5: How can national accreditation and qualification systems in regards to Open Science / Data skills for all be promoted?

1. By updating the European Digital Competence Framework with a view to including Open Science / Data related skills, minding for openness and FAIRness principles?
2. By developing a European Digital Data Skills Certificate (EDSC) that may be recognised and accepted by governments, employers, researchers, data professionals, trainers, and other stakeholders across Europe?
3. By developing a validation framework of these outcomes leading to micro-credentials or partial qualifications?

Responses:

- An ESOC certification of trainers, including soft and pedagogical skills, and of open environment for learning Open Science Skills sounds very promising. OPENness and FAIRness should apply to training courses
- Alignment of certification at national level is needed and involves national bodies for certification. Guidelines should be provided for MS/AC
- The role of accrediting bodies is critical. The multi-disciplinary nature of data related occupations requires drawing from the expertise of each of these bodies. Without strong cross-sector leadership and coordination, discrepancies in definitions of core knowledge, skills and behaviours will lead to inconsistent adoption of best practices
- At the institutional level, a certificate on responsible research/open science could work for the upskilling of researchers.

Question 6: How can soft skills (e.g on ethics) be nationally enhanced to relate with Open Science principles?

1. By establishing a formal Scientific Board responsible for providing credentials on research integrity pertaining to the integration of Open Science principles?
Development guidelines and an assessment framework with indicators for research performing organisations, aligned with relevant initiatives such as the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity?
2. By National Scientific Committees being responsible for ensuring the research integrity as regards to Open Science principles at MS/AC level?
3. By establishing an enabling environment for upskilling on research integrity practices, addressed mainly to Data Stewards and Researchers, for the application of Open Data/Science ethics standards to every research organization and research project, respecting GDPR & IPR limitations?

Responses:

- Ethics should be considered as core skills, even though not digital
- “Soft skills” is an unusual term for what can be very fine-grained knowledge; in addition, it can include expert knowledge of tooling e.g., for selecting an appropriate anonymisation tool
- Funding needs to be put into training (as well as infrastructure) and evidence needs to be gathered to demonstrate the difference it makes. Without this evidence, training/skills will always be seen as low priority and therefore not become sustainable
- The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity is actually under review to consider the research integrity and ethical standards
- The Scientific Board should be aligned to research integrity boards operating already at national level to produce credentials on Science being done properly that is Open Science.

Question 7: How can the development of Citizen Science be promoted and realised, at national level?

1. By promoting cultural change towards Open Science, through the organisation (and participation in) of various awareness raising and communication activities targeting mostly general public?
2. By introducing a European Open Science Skills week for schools and Universities?
3. By introducing European Open Science Skills day for citizens and general public?

Responses:

- Alignment with the way EC sees citizens' science is needed, along with alignment of the Horizon Europe financing and cascade funding: citizens' science initiatives based on the triple helix mechanism for stakeholders, accelerators, pilots, innovative approaches from citizens, recognition, institutional changes in Universities from promoting citizens science through collaboration with local communities
- Citizens campaigns need to be forecasted
- National points for citizens science are needed and should be organised; supporting them in their networking and collaboration with universities is promising. Standards are considered as important to this extent
- There is the EUA recommendation to be taken into consideration- Support, incentivise and reward citizen science - EUA calls on the Commission and EU member states to work with universities on providing the necessary support and developing adequate incentives and rewards to meaningfully engage in citizen science <https://eua.eu/resources/publications/949:perspectives-on-the-new-european-research-area-from-the-university-sector.html>;
- The term Skills in the EU week and day for Open Science needs to be clarified
- Establishment of Citizens Science Associations' networks need to be promoted at national level for supporting citizens' science
- Scientific communication and public engagement are important as skills for researchers to facilitate communication and awareness towards citizens. Training, assessment, incentives of researcher need to be considered this especially when researchers are involved in citizens' science initiatives
- There should be an Involvement of public and schools in citizens science to cure mistrust in certain research areas.

Question 8: How can an integrated at national level, robust, transparent, and participatory governance structure for digital skills on open science/access be established, at national and EU level?

1. By setting up of a Pact for Digital Skills (as referred to Digital Agenda), specific for Data Science, for the MS/AC to sign, minding for addressing the legal, ethical and IPR aspects, with the aim to mobilize and improve coherence in policy design efforts?
2. By proposing a participatory governance model, involving all respective stakeholders and governmental policy makers, considering the various different disciplines, minding for achieving alignment to the fast-changing technology?
3. By requiring National Coalitions on Digital Skills and Jobs to act as 'hubs' for close collaboration with other existing networks for research and training (i.e., network of libraries, Institutes, etc.) in order to facilitate a streamlined approach to digital upskilling, including Open Science upskilling?
4. By developing a human inter-operability model, in order to establish common interpretation of open science upskilling ecosystem and conceptualise a pan-European comprehensive governance and cooperation model

Responses:

- Something stronger than a Pact We might be needed to enforce a step forward for sound governance; many initiatives have already provided evidence and outcomes need to become more tangible now
- Co-research of stakeholders needs to be considered in upskilling.

Question 9: How can academia, research and industry be brought together for: (a) knowledge exchange to meet companies' research and (b) innovation needs and students' and researchers cross-disciplinary gain of experience, at national level?

1. By actively supporting the harmonisation of Digital Competences Centres' operation?
2. By creating blueprints for the cooperation of Academia-Industry-Public Sector on digital upskilling to define a certain share of a common training/knowledge content, focusing in domains such as AI, Cybersecurity, Open Science / Data?
3. By including content material for Open Science skills in the EU Digital Skills and Jobs Platform, that is currently under development, and EOSC being actively involved in the project?

Responses:

- The word 'blueprint' might be misleading, due to different interpretation in applied research and industry; A Common Principles' Guideline on Skills might be a more appropriate term
- The type of skills needed for this collaboration should have practical impact; it is not clear why this is important for researchers and just agreeing on the skills seems to make no difference. There needs to be an assessment on the kind of skills that are targeting industry and academia; the upskilling should also be related to training within collaborative projects on Open Science
- Digital Competences Centres': the systematic way for researchers and students is lying on academic curricula
- The human skills infrastructure is as important, or even more important, than the hardware but there is a lack of formal qualifications and recognition. In HPC the EU has tried funding virtual "centres of excellence" as a means of building capacity and it might be interesting to consider this option

Question 10: How can digital upskilling be complemented with a rigid readily available support network for Open Science practices and technical infrastructures, at national level?

How can the delivery and use of content platforms and learning environments be coordinated, at national level?

1. By developing integrated national innovative learning environments which incorporate on-line repositories/libraries and promote the co-development of supporting tools such as platforms, data testbeds, software for data creation, storage and sharing, etc. and build federated research data infrastructure
2. By building-up an integrated communication and delivery platform with scientific libraries
3. By developing national support networks of open science specialists: professional support staff, core specialists, legal experts, etc to serve researchers in practice
4. By concluding national open access license agreements with publishers

Responses:

- The first topic might seem overly ambitious to target and difficult to achieve
- The existing network of OpenAir experts should be considered within the network of science specialists, especially when it has proven its value
- Human infrastructure definitely needs to be reinforced; Individuals need to be supported with knowledge, resources, time, authority, expertise provided in some fields
- Support is crucial to institutions and research organisations with less critical mass, to correct imbalances
- Concluding national open access license agreements with publishers should be considered as a mid-term goal; Alternative environments for publications should be supported within these agreements; Interesting examples to explore are: Read & Publish contracts in the context of a dynamic scholarly publishing system <https://eua.eu/resources/publications/932:read-publish-agreements.html>, http://www.unica-network.eu/sites/default/files/unica_dechamp_2020_v2_0.pdf, <http://amelica.org/index.php/en/about/>, Amelica
- The scope of the agreements should be broadened; Open Research Europe platform should also be involved
- The Open Access challenge is global, other models should be explored to expand the fourth topic

- Scientific Libraries are the right stakeholders to support learning environments and promote learning in Open Science practice
- The collaboration of EOSC with GAIAX (a kind of EOSC for industry) should be explored.

Question 11: What should a leadership programme for EOSC digital skills in Open Science refer to?

1. By developing an action plan for the establishment of formal collaboration schemes with national policy making entities
2. By implementing and operating a maturity model for supporting the evidence-based appraisal and decision-making regarding effectiveness of Open Science upskilling policies and initiatives, at national level
3. By developing and proposing a composite indicator, or set of indicators, for Digital Skills in Open Science linked to existing ranking systems on monitoring scoreboard, such as e-DESI or Open Science Monitor
4. By developing a knowledge sharing platform, within the Knowledge/Education Hub, for the support of MS/AC and Research Organisations
5. By implementing networking and visibility initiatives on excellence and leadership in Open Science

Responses:

- The Leadership Program should include all recommendations so far, Open Science is broader than EOSC, allocation of tasks needs to be clear; The action plan needs to be practical and involve many stakeholders; the effort needed for its implementation seems important
- Knowledge/Education Hub needs to consider other initiatives in this ground
- Networking on excellence and leadership in Open Science should not stand alone as an effort and be bound to other networking initiatives.

3.4 Focus Groups' List of Participants

1. **Biljana Kosanovic** - University of Belgrade, Computer Centre (RCUB)
2. **Brina Klemenčič** – Slovenian NI4OS
3. **Paula Martinez Lavanchy** - Delft University of Technology; 4TU
4. **David Kane** - co-chair of the Irish National Skills WG,
5. **Dunja Legat** - University of Maribor Library, Slovenian NI4OS
6. **Iryna Kuchma** - Electronic Information for Libraries eIFL
7. **Mojca Kotar** -University of Lubjana
8. **Simone Mantovani** - NEANIAS project/MEE0
9. **Eloy Rodrigues** – University of Minho
10. **Marian Grootveld** - FAIRsFAIR/DANS/RDNL
11. **Matt Forshaw** - Newcastle University
12. **Miro Pušnik** - University of Lubjana
13. **Linden Farrer** - EC
14. **Sofoklis Sotiriou**, Ellinogermaniki Agogi
15. **Helen Clare**- JISK (British education and skills sectors' NGO)
16. **Paolo Budroni** - University of Vienna
17. **Jozsef Kovacs** - NEANIAS/SZTAKI

